

CRACKING THE CODE: THE EMOTIONAL LANGUAGE OF MUSIC

THE THEORY OF MUSICAL EQUILIBRATION
ANSWERS AN AGE-OLD QUESTION

BY

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How is it possible for music to evoke emotions? This is a question we often do not even ask ourselves: it seems completely natural for our feelings to be stirred up by music. The odd correlation between music and emotions is not something we think much about until

we actively consider what music really is. Strictly speaking, music is nothing other than a series of molecules in the air that are made to oscillate and make their way to the ear. But what do these oscillating molecules of air have to do with our feelings?

Studies on the effects of music are as old as music itself, and over the years different branches of science have focused on analyzing this issue. Back in the 19th century, a field known as ‘tone psychology’ took up the cause, followed by the 20th-century disciplines of music psychology and music physiology, which studied how the brain processes music. However, any-

one who had hoped that these developments would contribute to solving the puzzle ended up disappointed. Nowadays we even use highly sophisticated equipment and systematically structured research projects but we have yet to resolve the key question: how and why does music produce feelings?

For quite some time, the Theory of Musical Equilibration has astonished people with its assertion that music cannot convey emotions directly; instead, it simply expresses processes of the will with which the listener can identify. The theory states that identifying with these pro-

No progress despite highly sophisticated equipment

cesses gives them an emotional content. For example, when we hear a major chord, we identify with a process of the will that says, 'Yes, I want to', whereas in a minor chord the message is, 'No more'. This process of the will that states 'No more'

can be experienced as something sad or angry, depending on whether the minor chord is played quietly or loudly. The distinction here is the same as if someone were to whisper the words 'No more' quietly or if they were to shout them at

the top of their voice. The words sound sad when whispered and furious when shouted. The minor chord is the same: a quiet minor chord sounds resigned and a loud one, angry.

These kinds of processes of identifying with something are not only found in music. Something very similar can be observed when we watch television and identify with the processes of will that our favorite character expresses. Here too, relating to these processes generates emotions in us. All attempts to find the root cause of emotions in music itself failed until we realized that a 'detour' was involved, which led through will.

The Theory of Musical Equilibration offers a startling new insight: Music cannot communicate emotions directly; instead, it communicates processes of the will

THE THEORY OF MUSICAL EQUILIBRATION

Developed by music theorist Bernd Willimek, the Theory of Musical Equilibration (die Strebetendenz-Theorie) is the world's first well-structured approach used to outline the emotional character of different musical harmonies, and it is the first to postulate the rationale for the emotional effect they have. It was initially published in 1998 in the journal Tonkünstler-Forum Baden-Württemberg, Stuttgart (Germany), and presented in lectures, including one held in 1997 at the University of Rostock. The Theory of Musical Equilibration has yet to be refuted, and to date there is no equivalent scientific hypothesis.

The basic statement of the theory is that experiencing music emotionally has its roots in the listener identifying with processes of the will which are encoded in the music. The harmonies which are heard and anticipated interact with each other, presenting opportunities the Theory of Musical Equilibration has categorized systematically in such a way that even more complex and concrete processes of the will can be musically depicted. The manuscript 'Music and Emotions - Research on the Theory of Musical Equilibration' can be downloaded free of charge through the link > <http://www.willimekmusic.de/music-and-emotions.pdf>

How can we envision what a process of the will is like in music? It is related to the phenomena that earlier music-theory experts described in terms of suspended notes, leading notes and the urge towards musical resolution. As we listen to music, we sometimes anticipate the way one chord will lead to the next. The processes of the will are probably anchored in overtones – notes which also resonate when music is played, but as a rule they are not actively perceived and can have different impacts on the way we experience music.

Overtones yield the processes of will in music

DETERMINING THE EMOTIONAL CHARACTER OF EMOTIONS

In 1996, Bernd and Daniela Willimek began conducting surveys to learn how children judged the effects of different chords. They used these data as the basis for a wide-scale study in which over 2100 children from four continents have participated in musical preference tests. These tests were designed to find correlations between scenes from fairy tales and musical selections that described emotional terms. The most well-known participants in the tests included members of the Vienna Boys' Choir and the Regensburg Cathedral Choir.

Overall there was an 86% match, i.e. 86% of the participants correlated the musical selection to the emotion outlined by the Theory of Musical Equilibration as being the best match. As a supplement to the tests, the Willimeks also researched the repertoire of classical music and film scores to explore further links between music and emotions. Here they found conspicuous parallels which further confirmed their findings.

The Theory of Musical Equilibration hypothesizes that, to date, the effect of overtones has been misunderstood. Despite earlier beliefs to the contrary, it is not that we perceive changes in the notes: instead, we identify with the will that they express, and unlike previous premises, the notes want to remain unchanged. Something else remarkable is the fact that the notes are not perceived as what they really are – frequencies – but as something vague and uncertain.

THE TONAL CHARACTERS OF MUSICAL HARMONIES

The fundamental principle of the Theory of Musical Equilibration is quite simple at first. Chords are traditionally described in many textbooks as having 'striving' notes, i.e. notes that want to be resolved. This sense of striving, however, is a contradictory desire. For example, the real musical experience we have when we hear a C-major

chord is not the effort of the E to resolve. Instead, the defining musical experience is identifying with the will for the E not to change – to allow it to keep resonating as it is. If we want to apply this idea with great-

er nuance in a musical context, we may also need to take into account the preceding or subsequent harmonies, if not also the harmonies anticipated. Below we will discuss the nature of some of the chords as deter-

mined by the Theory of Musical Equilibration. More information on the interpretation of these emotional characters can be found in the manuscript 'Music and Emotions - Research on the Theory of Musical Equilibration'.

WHY DO MAJOR CHORDS SOUND CHEERFUL?

The Theory of Musical Equilibration states that when we hear a major chord, we identify with a process of the will that says, 'Yes, I want to'. In emotional terms, we can describe this process of the will as 'identifying with a feeling of sober-minded contentment with the present moment', a sense of satisfaction.

There are, however, other qualities the major chord can evoke

as well: we will address those below.

A major chord can express a feeling of being content

Major chord

WHY HAVE WE ALWAYS ASSOCIATED MINOR CHORDS WITH A SENSE OF SORROW?

Why do minor chords sound sad? Several music theorists do not regard the minor chord as a harmonic interval of its own; instead, they see it as a 'suppressed' or clouded major chord, since the third in the chord is simply lower than in the major chord. If we apply this thought to the Theory of Musical Equilibration, that means a suppressed version of the major chord leads to a 'clouded' feeling of being content with the present moment. Contentment turns into discontentment, a sense of 'no more'. The minor chord thus seems sad when played quietly and full of anger when played loudly. If a minor chord

is first repeated quietly and then at increasing speed and volume, you can experience a remarkable transfor-

mation from hearing an expression of sorrow to an expression of anger.

Minor chord

Play this chord several times, first quietly and then at increasing volume and speed. You will notice the striking shift from a sense of sorrow to a sense of fury.

MAJOR CHORDS CAN SOUND JUST AS SAD AS MINOR CHORDS

Musicology has not yet managed to find an explanation as to why minor chords feel sad, and consequently it was truly overwhelmed when it came to analyzing why major chords can also sound mournful. Major chords can seem sad if a sorrowful-sounding minor chord is used as their dominant.

If the chords below are repeated several times, the listener begins to anticipate the minor chord as the major chord is still sounding, resulting in the major chord taking on the character of a minor chord. It then seems just as sad as a minor chord.

Dominant

Minor chord

Alternate between quietly playing the chord on the left and the chord on the right several times. As you do so, pay attention to the effect of the major chord on the right. You will notice that after a short while, this chord sounds just as sad as the minor chord on the left, despite the fact that it is a major chord. Here the major chord assumes the character of a minor chord.

NATURAL MINOR IS THE PERFECT MATCH FOR HIGH TENSION

Minor chords can evoke emotions other than sorrow and anger. The music from the movie *Pirates of the Caribbean* is a well-known example: the theme is played in minor, or more specifically in what is called natural minor. This harmonic mode sounds adventurous and courageous. Children who were asked their impressions of this chord used words such as 'excitement', 'Wild West' and 'thriller'. The terms they used kept revolving around the ideas of adventure, courage and danger.

Nearly every TV thriller uses the impact of the minor chord to generate tension in the theme music and in exciting scenes. Beyond that, this harmonic device is what shapes the downright bold-sounding character of natural minor when used in

rock and pop music (Deep Purple, Santana). In commercial esoteric music for meditation, this chord is played at low volume to express a sense of letting yourself go and embarking on a meditative adventure. The courage-inspiring effect of the chords is intended to evoke responsiveness to our feelings and new spiritual experiences.

Natural minor

Play the highlighted notes in whatever sequence you like. When you play them quietly, they will remind you of a meditative adventure, whereas when they are played loudly, they can be used to accentuate an exciting thriller.

THE DOMINANT CHORD BRINGS MOTION INTO MUSIC

When a major chord is alternated with a dominant chord (see image below right), the listener receives information that seems contradictory. It resolves this conflict by integrating both impressions into an impression of forward motion. Nearly every wandering song uses this harmonic progression to create a sense of moving.

Major chord

Dominant

Alternate between these chords many times, and you will have a sense of being part of forward motion.

THE SUBDOMINANT IS THE SOUND OF TRANQUILITY

The subdominant chord (image below right) is used in classical and pop music to communicate a relaxed and untroubled mood. It is frequently used at melodic high points. Passages with subdominant chords in songs of different kinds were also described in surveys as being the most

'untroubled' and 'joyful'.

This sentiment goes well with moments of lightheartedness, such as those which occur in a rapturous state or after a victory. That means that the subdominant is also excellent for songs sung

at cheerful occasions, and its use is widespread in this context. The subdominant is also well-suited to depicting a light-hearted mood in children's songs. In many national anthems, the subdominant emphasizes the emotional apex of the song.

Major chord

Subdominant

Start by playing the chord on the left several times to get used to the key. Then play the chord on the right and allow it to unfold its effect. You will sense your mood brightening.

Major chord

Subdominant major 7th

First play the chord on the left a few times to establish the key. Then play the chord on the right, and you will notice a sense of wistfulness. Every musical epoch from the Baroque era onward has taken advantage of this effect.

THE SUBDOMINANT WITH A MAJOR SEVENTH CONVEYS WISTFULNESS

This chord clearly illustrates that the emotional effect of harmonies has remained fundamentally the same across the centuries. The subdominant with a major seventh sounds downright wistful, regardless of whether it occurs in the Johann Sebastian Bach's Air, the choral piece 'Abschied vom Walde'

by Felix Mendelssohn Bartholdy or in Elton John's 'Your Song.' In many pieces, this harmonic device is a means of generating a sense of pensiveness.

THE SEVENTH CHORD WAS PART OF THE COUNTERCULTURAL REVOLUTION

When a seventh chord (see image below) is played at a loud volume, it creates a sensation of being rebellious and defiant. In the 20th century, this musical device provided a new way for the younger generation to revolt against the values of the establishment. Prior to that, the spirit of rebellion it expressed was aimed across racial lines in North America. The blues patterns, which are built on these harmonies, sound rebellious and defiant through their chords alone.

The explosive musical effect of what was once considered an anti-establishment anthem, the Rolling Stones'

'(I Can't Get No) Satisfaction', came from the sevenths in the chords and the melody. If these sevenths were removed from the melody and replaced with another note, the melody would suddenly lose its revolutionary nature, and at best it would be suitable as a rock anthem. By contrast, if the seventh were to be played quietly, the piece would take on an entirely different character. It would come across as plaintive, weepy or weak.

Seventh chord

If you play the highlighted notes of this chord at a loud volume, they have the character of rebellion or revolt. At a lower volume they feel more weepy or weak.

THE ADDED SIXTH IN A MAJOR CHORD EXPRESSES WARMTH AND SECURITY

The added sixth in a major chord, can convey profound togetherness, a feeling of warmth and emotional solace. Even Ludwig van Beethoven made use of this effect, and in today's pop music, the chord continues to create the same impression.

The chord does not always have this effect, however. There is a small trick which inverts its character, however when this happens, the chord does not express comfort, but a feeling of being forlorn. The decisive point here is the listener's orientation towards the key of

the piece. The following examples demonstrate the point:

Portrait of Ludwig van Beethoven

Major chord (D-major)

Added sixth (major)

Play the chord on the left a few times to establish the tonic. Then play the chord on the right and see how it affects you. You can almost envision a mental image of being cuddled up next to a cozy fire with someone you love, enjoying a sense of contentment and security.

Major chord (F-major)

Added sixth (major)

Here again, play the chord on the left to establish the key as a baseline. When you play the chord on the right, something surprising will happen. Even though this is exactly the same chord as in the previous example, its emotional impact has changed completely. The same notes no longer seem to express warmth and comfort: they convey the very opposite, a sense of feeling lost.

THE ADDED SIXTH IN A MINOR CHORD REPRESENTS HEARTBREAK

In a minor chord, the added sixth has exactly the opposite emotional effect of the added sixth in major. It is employed to express painful loneliness and heartbreak. Franz Schubert effectively deployed this chord as well: it appears at the beginning of his sorrowful song cycle Winterreise during the first words, 'Fremd bin ich eingezogen'.

Minor chord

Added sixth (minor)

First play the chord on the left to become acclimatized to the key. When you hear the chord on the right, you can relate to a sense of loneliness.

or 'someone running away from a monster in the forest'. The frightful effect of this chord was familiar as far back as Johann Sebastian Bach. In St. Matthew's Passion, he used this harmony at the very moving moment when Pontius Pilate asked the crowd who should be released, Jesus or the criminal Barrabas, and the crowd screams, 'Barrabas!'. The same chord can be heard at the word "tears" in Stevie Wonder's song 'Joy Inside My Tears'. When the chord is played quietly, a spirit of melancholy brooding is evoked.

THE DIMINISHED SEVENTH CHORD COMMUNICATES FRIGHT AND DESPAIR

The diminished seventh chord is a solid device for creating a feeling of fright in listeners. Tense scenes of horror in movies are heightened with diminished sevenths, and this happens frequently in scores. When children were asked what this chord made them think of, they responded with answers such as 'something horrible', 'somebody having a nervous breakdown'

The diminished seventh chord

When you play a diminished seventh quietly, it is reminiscent of melancholy brooding. If it is played at a louder volume, it can be used to underscore the scenes in horror movies in which shocking things occur.

A MIRACLE HAPPENING – THE AUGMENTED CHORD IS FULL OF ASTONISHMENT

The defining characteristic of an augmented chord (see image below) is that it contains dissonance which wants to resolve, but the resolution it seeks cannot be readily identified. Applying the Theory of Musical Equilibration thus leads to an equally unclear outcome: identifying with processes of the will is a vague and

unclear procedure. The listener assumes the role of a questioner and identifies with a feeling of astonishment and amazement. This also describes the emotional character of the augmented chord.

In movies, this is an effective way of calling attention to miraculous things happening in the

story. In cartoons in particular, augmented chords can frequently be heard when magic is performed in the story. In *Winterreise*, Franz Schubert uses the augmented chord at the very moment the word 'wunderliches' is sung in the 'Die Krähe' ('The Crow').

Augmented chord

With its combination of consonance and dissonance, the augmented chord conveys a feeling of surprise because the three notes of its triad cannot be clearly interpreted. In film scores this chord can be heard when something remarkable or magical takes place.

THE WHOLE-TONE SCALE FEELS WEIGHTLESS

The whole-tone scale, which is commonly used in Impressionist music, can yield a feeling of weightlessness. In film scores, these chords are primarily a way to musically illustrate states of floating such as scenes that take place under water, in space, or in a subjectively buoyant state: dreams.

The whole-tone scale

In Impressionism, the whole-tone scale is used to convey a feeling of weightlessness. If you play the highlighted notes in any given sequence, you will notice a sense of floating.

THE MINOR SIXTH EXPRESSES A SENSE OF FEAR

A feeling can be inspired in the listener not only with a chord: two notes can also be enough to generate this effect. If you play a minor sixth (see image below) quietly, the dyad can create an unusual sense of fearfulness

Minor sixth

A minor sixth can generate a mood of fearfulness

A NEW WAY OF UNDERSTANDING MUSIC

The issue of the emotional effects that musical harmonies have is as relevant as ever. Centuries of composers have been using harmonic structures in keeping with the observations described in the Theory of Musical Equilibration, which is quite remarkable. This gives researchers an endless field of new activities and a wide range of opportunities due to the rich scope of untapped material. The Theory of Musical Equilibration is to inspire further interest in one of the most exciting aspects of musicology: the emotional response to musical harmonies.